

A large, abstract graphic in the top left corner consisting of a yellow-to-orange gradient circle partially enclosed by a thick blue line that curves downwards and to the right.

Item Library: **Technical guidelines**

Second edition 2025

on behalf of the
EORTC Quality of Life Group

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Abbreviations used in the document

CAT – Computerised Adaptive Testing

CTCAE – Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events

EORTC – European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer

IL – Item Library

QLD – Quality of Life Department

QLG – Quality of Life Group

Introduction to the Item Library: history and development

The main aim of the Item Bank, as it was originally called, was to create a database of items that could be used, mainly by the QLG members, during the process of new questionnaire development. It enabled investigators to browse through validated items, identify questions covering relevant issues that they wanted to include, and use them in new instruments with consistent wording. This way, the Item Bank also saved time and effort spent on the translation process by re-using previously translated items.

With technological advances requiring updates of the software, the Item Bank underwent subsequent refurbishments in 2009 and 2016.

In 2017, the Item Bank was renamed as the Item Library and gained a new functionality: the option of making a custom item list from the items available in the database. All such user-made item lists are available for browsing and re-using. In further stages of development, two classifications of items were added to facilitate item selection based on their content and relation to the Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE).

Item Library overview

In its current form, the IL enables users to:

1. Browse through the existing official EORTC instruments (including EORTC CAT Core item banks and short forms) as well as user-created custom item lists,
2. Find existing items for new item lists from the pool of items developed by the QLG, consult information about the items and language availability,
3. Make a custom item list from selected items.

Access

How to get access to the Item Library:

1. Go to <https://itemlibrary.eortc.org/>
2. Fill the request access form in, specifying your name, institution/company where you work, your e-mail address, motivation for accessing the IL and the type of account you are requesting (academic, commercial or for an active QLG member).

EORTC Quality of Life Group Item Library

The Item Library is a database of items used in fully and partially validated EORTC quality of life questionnaires.

This tool has been created by the EORTC Quality of Life Group with the primary aim of being used during the development of new instruments.

Developers can access it to see how items were formulated in previous questionnaires and to reuse existing validated items and their translations.

Access to the Item Library can also be granted to academic and commercial users as a reference tool.

A login form with the following elements: a "Log In" heading, an "Email" label above a text input field, a "Password" label above another text input field, a blue "Log in" button, a "Forgot your password?" link, and a "No account? Request access" link which is highlighted with a red border.

3. Your request is automatically sent to the IL admin, who will prepare an access agreement and send it to you for signature. Access to the IL is free of charge for all users.
4. Upon receipt of a fully executed agreement, the IL admin activates the account.

Types of accounts

There are three types of accounts with a different level of access to the IL's functionalities:

1. QLG: full access to all features (searching English items and all translations), limited in time by the duration of the active membership in the QLG
2. Academic: full access to all features (searching English items and all translations), valid for 6 months from activation
3. Commercial: access to English items, valid for 3 months from activation

Logging in

The login page's address is <https://itemlibrary.eortc.org/>

On the login page, you can:

1. Request access by filling in the access form,
2. Log in with your e-mail address and password chosen during the registration process,

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A login form with the following elements: a "Log In" heading, an "Email" label above a text input field, a "Password" label above another text input field, a blue "Log in" button, a "Forgot your password?" link, and a "No account? Request access" link.

3. Receive a new temporary password by clicking on “Forgot your password?”. The process is fully automatic and is the only way to get a new password, since the IL admin does not have access to the password database.

Item Library home page

Total number of questionnaires and unique items → 162 questionnaires, 1075 questions

← Search box

Official questionnaires Custom questionnaires Item classification

A

- AYA Adolescents And Young Adults module (30 questions)
- ANL Anal module (28 questions)

B

- BLM Bladder module (30 questions)
- BM Bone Metastases module (22 questions)
- BN Brain module (20 questions)
- BR23 Breast previous (23 questions)
- BR Breast module (42 questions)
- BRECON Breast Reconstruction module (23 questions)

C

- CAT AP CAT Appetite cat (7 questions)
- CAT CF CAT Cognitive Functioning cat (34 questions)
- CAT CO CAT Constipation cat (10 questions)
- CAT DI CAT Diarrhea cat (13 questions)
- CAT DY CAT Dyspnea cat (32 questions)
- CAT FF CAT Emotional Functioning cat (24 questions)
- CAT FA CAT Fatigue cat (34 questions)
- CAT FI CAT Financial Difficulties cat (9 questions)

Welcome to the Item Library!

The **Core questionnaire** QLQ-C30 has been developed to assess the quality of life of cancer patients. It is supplemented by disease-, symptom- and population-specific questionnaires called **modules**. You can also find general questionnaires that can be used without the Core questionnaire, called **standalones**.

Previous versions are questionnaires that have been updated.

The **CAT** groups all item banks for the Computer Adapted Testing system.

Categories

- All
- Core questionnaires
- Modules
- Standalone questionnaires
- Previous versions (questionnaires)
- CAT
- CAT short forms
- Short forms

Types of official questionnaires

The home page of the IL consists of the following elements:

- The total number of questionnaires (official EORTC instruments) and unique items included in the Item Library
- Search box
- Tab allowing switching between the view of the official EORTC questionnaires, the custom-made questionnaires library, and the item classification
- List of types of official questionnaires – clicking on the category acts as a filter to display only the chosen category:

- Core – the C30 as the core questionnaire with 30 items relevant to the general population of cancer patients and the C15-PAL, an abbreviated version of the C30 for palliative patients. The C15-PAL questionnaire is shorter to focus on the issues relevant in a palliative setting and to diminish patient burden
- Stand-alone questionnaires – questionnaires which can be used on their own, without the C30
- Modules – site-, population- and symptom-specific questionnaires that complement the C30 and should always be used together with the core
- Previous versions – previously developed questionnaires which have been updated ever since
- CAT – the EORTC Computer-Adaptive Testing (CAT) Core version of the 15 domains of the QLQ-C30 questionnaire. This category includes full item banks (all items comprising the item banks)
- CAT short forms – the EORTC CAT Core short forms created from the CAT item banks

Footer

<p>How to obtain the questionnaires</p> <p>The EORTC has two policies for the use of the QLQ-C30 and associated modules.</p> <p>Commercial users ⓘ - Royalty fee: please contact qol.contracts@eortc.org</p> <p>What is classed as 'academic' research ⓘ - for educational institutions, hospitals, etc - No fee: questionnaires can be downloaded from the EORTC website</p>	<p>Can't find what you're looking for?</p> <p>Please suggest some issues that are not yet captured in questions. ⓘ</p> <p>Contact us at itemlibrary@eortc.org</p>
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The footer consists of two columns:

- Information on how to obtain official questionnaires – both for academic and commercial use
- Contact information for sending suggestions of items that were not found in the existing pool of questions

Overview of the Official questionnaires library

Types of views

Questionnaire view

162 questionnaires, 1075 questions

search the item library...

Include custom questionnaires from the community

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- Short forms

You can see the full questionnaire in its validated form by clicking the icon on the homepage or the title of a questionnaire. You can also search with the name or other keywords in the search box and select the questionnaire of choice. If you want to see all questionnaires in a certain category – for example, Modules – you can use the list of categories to filter the list of questionnaires on the left.

The questionnaire view includes the following elements:

- General information on the questionnaire
- List of the items – clicking on an item shows its basic information view
- All other elements included in the questionnaire – conditions, instructions, response scale(s), time frame(s), and domain scales with the option of filtering
- Additional information about the questionnaire (if available – under all items)

The screenshot shows the 'Brain' module interface. At the top, there is a header with 'BN 20' and 'Brain' title. Below the title, there are several metadata fields: GENDER (Neutral), TYPE (Module), CONTACT (itemlibrary@eortc.be), TESTING (Phase IV completed), and LAST MODIFIED (05 Jan 2018). On the right side of the header, there are icons for '+ Add item', a folder icon, a download icon, a trash icon, and an edit icon.

The main content area is divided into two sections. On the left, under the 'Questions' tab, there is a list of 12 items (numbered 31 to 42) with their respective text and icons for editing and deleting. The items are:

- 31. Did you feel uncertain about the future?
- 32. Did you feel you had setbacks in your condition?
- 33. Were you concerned about disruption of family life?
- 34. Did you have headaches?
- 35. Did your outlook on the future worsen?
- 36. Did you have double vision?
- 37. Was your vision blurred?
- 38. Did you have difficulty reading because of your vision?
- 39. Did you have seizures?
- 40. Did you have weakness on one side of your body?
- 41. Have you had trouble finding the right words to express yourself?
- 42. Did you have difficulty speaking?

On the right, under the 'Questionnaire info' tab, there is a 'Description' section titled 'QLQ-BN20 Brain module'. The description states: 'The QLQ-BN20 Brain module is meant for use among brain cancer patients varying in disease stage and treatment modality (i.e. surgery, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, etc.). This module is to be used with the EORTC QLQ-C30 core questionnaire. The BN20 module is fully validated.'

Below the description is an 'Instructions' section with two bullet points:

- Patients sometimes report that they have the following symptoms. (with a filter icon)
- Please indicate the extent to which you have experienced these symptoms or problems during the past week. (with a filter icon)

Next is a 'Response scales' section with one bullet point:

- Not at all, A little, Quite a bit, Very much (with a filter icon for Q. 31-50)

Then is a 'Time scales' section with one bullet point:

- During the past week (with a filter icon for Q. 31-50)

Finally, there is a 'Domain scales' section with two bullet points:

- Future uncertainty - scale (with a filter icon for Q. 31-33,35)
- Visual disorder - scale (with a filter icon for Q. 36-38)

Detailed questionnaire view

The screenshot shows the 'Detailed questionnaire view' for a questionnaire titled 'Brain'. The interface includes a header bar with the following information: 'BN 20', 'GENDER Neutral', 'TYPE Module', 'CONTACT itemlibrary@eortc.be', 'TESTING Phase IV completed', and 'LAST MODIFIED 05 Jan 2018'. Below the header, there are two tabs: 'Questions' (selected) and 'Questionnaire info'. The 'Questions' tab displays a list of six questions, each with a three-dot menu icon to its right. The 'Questionnaire info' tab is active, showing a 'Description' section with the text: 'QLQ-BN20 Brain module. The QLQ-BN20 Brain module is meant for use among brain cancer patients varying in disease stage and treatment modality (i.e. surgery, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, etc.). This module is to be used with the EORTC QLQ-C30 core questionnaire. The BN20 module is fully validated.' Below the description is an 'Instructions' section with a bullet point: 'Patients sometimes report that they have the following symptoms.' To the right of the instructions is a filter control with 'all' and 'filter' buttons. A red box highlights the 'English' language selection in the 'Questions' tab, the 'Description' section, and the filter control.

The detailed questionnaire view contains the following elements and functionalities:

- Basic information about the questionnaire
- Description of the questionnaire
- Tab to switch the language in which the questionnaire is displayed
- A full list of the items
- A full list of elements such as instructions, time frame(s), response scale(s), domain scale(s) with options to filter the view.

1. Basic information

The screenshot shows the 'Basic information' section for the 'Brain' questionnaire. It features a header bar with the following information: 'BN 20', 'GENDER Neutral', 'TYPE Module', 'CONTACT itemlibrary@eortc.be', 'TESTING Phase IV completed', and 'LAST MODIFIED 05 Jan 2018'. A red box highlights the 'Brain' title and the 'GENDER Neutral' information.

- Gender – specifies the gender of the population in which the questionnaire was originally validated
- Type – type of questionnaire: core, module, standalone, CAT, previous version.
- Contact – e-mail address for any questions related to the questionnaire

- Testing – phase of development following the EORTC Module Development Guidelines:
 - Phase III completed – pilot-testing phase finished and approved
 - In Phase IV – undergoing Phase IV field-testing
 - Phase IV completed – fully validated with the Phase IV field-test finished and approved
 - “Last modified” date
2. Main description – basic information on the questionnaire
 3. Filter view for:
 - Conditions – for items which should be answered only under certain conditions
 - Instructions
 - Time scale
 - Response scale
 - Domain scale

Clicking on the “filter” button shows which items are defined by each element. Clicking on “clear” turns off the filtered view.

4. Language version – list of all available linguistically validated translations. Selecting a language shows all elements in the chosen language with English version underneath.
5. Other information:
 - Any additional details on the questionnaire and its use
 - References of development and validation publications
 - References of other publications on the questionnaire and its translations

Item view

Basic information view

The basic information on an item is shown in the “Question details” tab and includes:

The screenshot displays the 'Item view' interface for a questionnaire. At the top, there is a header for 'Brain' with a 'BN 20' badge. Below this, several metadata fields are shown: GENDER (Neutral), TYPE (Module), CONTACT (itemlibrary@eortc.be), TESTING (Phase IV completed), and LAST MODIFIED (05 Jan 2018). The main content area is divided into two tabs: 'Questionnaire info' and 'Question details', with the latter being active. On the left, a list of questions is shown, with question 31 highlighted. On the right, the details for question 31 are displayed, including the question text, direction (negative), issue (feeling uncertain about one's future), response scales (Not at all, A little, Quite a bit, Very much), time scales (During the past week), and domain scales (Future uncertainty - scale). A 'See all info' button is located at the bottom of the details panel.

- Number in the questionnaire
- Wording in the questionnaire
- Direction of scoring – negative (symptom scale) or positive (functional scale)
- Underlying issue of the item
- Recommended wording for the item (if set)
- Response scales associated with the item in the context of the questionnaire
- Time frames associated with the item in the context of the questionnaire
- Domain scale to which the item belongs in the context of the questionnaire

- See all info – button to see the detailed information page on the item.

Switching back to the questionnaire view is possible by clicking on the “Questionnaire info” tab.

Detailed item view

Q116 - lost hair

Question - Direction: negative ⓘ - Issue: losing hair

hair loss alopecia scalp body

Translated into 120 languages

English

Recommended wording

Have you lost any hair?

From: [Breast, Breast, Multiple Myeloma](#) and 5 others...

Other wordings

Have you had hair loss?

From: [Chronic Myeloid Leukaemia, Lung, Lung](#)

Have you lost hair as a result of your treatment?

From: [Colorectal](#)

Have you lost hair?

From: [Endometrial](#)

...

Have you lost hair?

From: [Chronic Myeloid Leukaemia, Lung, Lung](#)

Have you lost hair as a result of your treatment?

From: [Colorectal](#)

Have you lost hair?

From: [Endometrial](#)

Specified by

This questions is typically specified by:

- 🕒 During the past week:
- 📊 Not at all, A little, Quite a bit, Very much
- ⓘ There are no right or wrong answers.
- ⓘ We are interested in some things about you and your health.
- ⓘ Please answer all of the questions yourself by circling the number that best applies to you.
- ⓘ Patients sometimes report that they have the following symptoms or problems.
- ⓘ Please indicate the extent to which you have experienced these symptoms or problems during the past week.
- ⓘ Please answer by circling the number that best applies to you.
- 📄 Systemic chemotherapy side effects - scale

and 4 others...

Similar questions

The following questions have a similar wording.

- ? Were you upset by the loss of your hair?
- ? If so, were you upset by the loss of your hair?

- ? Have you been upset by the loss of your hair?
- ? Did hair loss bother you?

The full item view page includes:

- Code – unique code for each item
- Short name
- Direction of scoring – negative (symptom scale) or positive (functional scale)
- Underlying issue
- Keywords

- Language versions – a drop-down list of all available translations of the item
- Wordings – all wordings for the item as used in various questionnaires over time. Recommended wording (if set) is based on linguistic aspects (such as the use of a more suitable grammatical tense) and comprehensibility (simpler terms etc.). For other wordings, the top one is the most recently added. Wordings are marked as gender-specific, if they originate from a gender-specific questionnaire. The same mechanism is used to show wordings in other languages, with a possible recommended wording and the top wording being the most recently added (thus from the most recently finalized translation).
- Three dots – functionality allowing adding a wording to a custom questionnaire
- Specified by – a list of other elements that are used with this item in all questionnaires and scales in which the item is included.
- Similar questions – a list of similarly worded questions. The similarity is computed as a percentage of overlapping words, thus it is not based on similarity of meaning. It can help make items consistent and re-use parts of translations.

Other elements – response scales, time scales, conditions, instructions, domain scales

In the questionnaire view, it is possible to filter additional elements such as response scales to see which items they describe in the questionnaire. Clicking on the element shows its full information page.

RS1 - 4-point Likert scale

ResponseScale

Translated into 141 languages

English

Recommended wording

Not at all, A little, Quite a bit, Very much

From: [Adolescents and Young Adults, Anal, Bladder](#) and 152 others...

...

Specifies

This response scale is typically specified by:

- ? Have you felt less masculine as a result of your disease or treatment?
- ? Have you urinated frequently during the day?
- ? Has weight loss been a problem for you?
- ? Do you have any trouble doing strenuous activities, like carrying a heavy shopping bag or a suitcase?
- ? Do you have any trouble taking a long walk?
- ? Do you have any trouble taking a short walk outside of the house?
- ? Were you limited in doing either your work or other daily activities?
- ? Do you need to stay in bed or a chair during the day?
- ? Do you need help with eating, dressing, washing yourself or using the toilet?

and 844 others...

Similar questions

The following questions have a similar wording.

Not at all, A little, Quite a bit, Very much, Not Applicable

N/A, Not at all, A little, Quite a bit, Very much

The full information page includes:

- Name and code
- Category
- Language versions
- Wordings – all wordings used for the particular element in all questionnaires. The recommended wording is marked for the wording that should be used in new item lists
- List of items this element specifies
- Similarly worded elements

Searching

Searching is the basic function of the Item Library. It enables you to find items or questionnaires that are of interest and cover the relevant issues.

General searching in the Item Library can be done two-fold:

- With the search box on the home page, or
- By browsing through the questionnaires and items.

Home page search box

The search box on the Item Library home page can be used in several ways.

When you start typing your search words, a drop-down list appears with the following options:

- Existing keywords
- Items that match the typed word(s) because the name or wording includes them or the word matches one of the keywords associated with this item
- Questionnaires that match the typed word(s)
- Other elements of questionnaires that match the typed word(s).

When you type a search word, you can do two things:

1. Type your search term and click Enter to get search results;
2. Choose from the list of the existing keywords and items/questionnaires/etc. the one that matches your search criteria. If you choose a keyword (term with a looking glass),

you will arrive at the results page for a search performed with that term. If you choose a matching item/questionnaire/etc., you will see a page with the information on that item/questionnaire/etc.

The icons to the left of the term represent the category of the entry:

	Condition (CS)
	Instruction (IN)
	Question (Q)
	Questionnaire (code derived from the title)
	Response scale (RS)
	Domain scale (DS)
	Time scale (TS)

Each entry in the IL has its code based on its type as listed above (for example, Q151, RS5, TS3), and it is possible to use it as a search term.

Search results

Search results are displayed with a predefined filter on questionnaires and items, so that only questionnaires and items that fulfil the search criteria are shown. It is possible to show other types of results by enabling and disabling filters by ticking respective boxes on the right-hand side.

Include custom questionnaires from the community

Search result for "pain"

Add 0 selected to questionnaire

- **painkillers**
Did you take any medicine for pain?
in [Head & Neck](#), [Lung](#)
- **pain not relieved by medication**
Have you had pain not relieved by pain medications?
in [Bone Metastases](#)
- **CAT Pain**
cat (16 questions)
- **pain while lying down**
Have you had pain while lying down?
in [Bone Metastases](#)
- **pain while sitting**
Have you had pain while sitting?
in [Anal](#), [Bone Metastases](#)

Filters

- Condition (0)
- Instruction (0)
- Question (120)
- Questionnaire (1)
- Response scale (0)
- Domain scale (19)
- Time scale (1)

Keywords

Each item has a list of associated keywords that help the search engine. Keywords are shown in the item view and can be used to trigger a search action. Clicking on a keyword leads to a search results page listing all elements associated with this keyword.

 Q70 - dry mouth
Question - Direction: negative ⓘ - Issue: having a dry mouth

dryness thirsty parched xerostomia lack of saliva sticky saliva salivary

Overview of the Custom questionnaires library

Types of custom questionnaires

The screenshot shows the 'Custom questionnaires' section of a library. At the top, there are two tabs: 'Official questionnaires' and 'Custom questionnaires', with the latter being selected. Below the tabs, there is a '+ Create a new questionnaire' button. The main content is divided into two sections: 'My questionnaires' and 'Questionnaires from community'. Under 'My questionnaires', there are three items: 'BIL21 modified Draft questionnaire (21 questions)', 'BLM modified Draft questionnaire Waiting for approval', and 'Brain BN20+2 Custom questionnaire (20 questions)'. Under 'Questionnaires from community', there is one item: 'Bone Metastases modified Custom questionnaire (22 questions)'.

The Custom questionnaire library is divided into two sections:

- My questionnaires
- Questionnaires from community.

My questionnaires

There are three types of item lists in the My questionnaires section:

- Drafts – visible only to the user who created them
- Waiting for approval – visible to the user who created it and to the content manager/IL admin
- Approved – visible to all users

Questionnaires from community

The Questionnaires from community section includes two types of questionnaires:

- Approved custom item lists made by other users,
- Approved custom item lists made by you.

Custom item list flow

In order to make a new custom item list you should follow these steps:

1. Make a new questionnaire – fill in the basic information form
2. Add items
3. Add response scale, time scale, instructions, conditions if necessary
4. Submit for approval
5. Content manager/admin checks the information and the questionnaire – in case of problems contacts the user and edits if necessary. There is also a user agreement sent for signature.
6. Questionnaire is approved – it becomes visible to all users and can be downloaded as a .csv file.

Make your own item list

There are a few ways to create a custom item list.

1. By making a copy of an existing questionnaire and adding/deleting items – in order to make a copy you should choose the questionnaire to be copied and click on the “Copy as new custom questionnaire” button visible in the questionnaire’s view

2. By creating a new questionnaire from the home page – simply click on the “Create a new questionnaire” button

3. By creating a new item list in the “Custom questionnaires” library

4. By adding search results to a new questionnaire – once search results have been selected, you can click on “Add X selected to questionnaire” and from the drop-down list chose “New questionnaire”

- By adding an item from the questionnaire view – if an item from a particular questionnaire seems of interest, you can click on the three dots and add it to an empty item list by selecting “New questionnaire”

- By adding a wording from the item view – if a particular wording in an item view seems of interest, you can click on the three dots and add it to an empty item list by selecting “New questionnaire”

Custom item list details

When creating a new item list, you have to fill in some basic information about your questionnaire. The following information can be filled in:

Add Questionnaire

✕

Your questionnaire will be saved as a draft.

If you wish to export this questionnaire for use, you will first need to submit it for approval. Once a content manager approves it, it will be visible to the entire community and everyone will be able to export it for use.

Name	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="e. g. Breast Module"/>
Type	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="Item list"/>
Gender	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="Neutral"/>
Molecule	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="Name of the molecule tested"/>
First question	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="1"/>
	The numbering of questions starts from this number.
Description	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"><div style="display: flex; gap: 5px; border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc; margin-bottom: 5px;">H1H2Normal⌵BIU☰☷🔗℥</div><div style="padding: 5px;">any other information worth mentioning...</div></div>

- Name – chosen name (can be changed later)
- Type – a drop-down list to choose, Item list is set as the default type.
- Gender – gender of the population for which the item list is intended.
- Molecule – name of the molecule that will be tested with the item list. It is not obligatory.
- Description – place for any information deemed necessary. The more information you can provide, the easier it is for the IL admin to review your item list.

NOTE: names of the authors of custom item lists are not stored or visible to other users, regardless of their profile and status of the questionnaire. If the author wants to mark authorship, any information on the questionnaire can be added in the description but is subject to review and change by the IL admin.

Add items to a custom item list

There are various ways to add an item to an already created item list:

1. In the custom item list view in the Custom Questionnaires library

2. From search results by clicking the three dots icon and selecting the item list of choice
3. From questionnaire view by clicking the three dots icon and selecting the item list of choice
4. From item view by clicking the three dots icon and selecting the item list of choice

Delete items from a custom item list

In order to delete any item from an item list you have to click on the item you want to delete and then click on the garbage bin icon. You will be then asked to confirm that the item should be deleted.

Re-order items

While it is not advisable to change the order of items if multiple items from one questionnaire/scale are used, it is possible to re-order them in a custom item list. In order to move an item to another location in the list, you have to click on the dots to the left of the wording and drag the item to its new place. The numbering of the list should update on its own, but in case it has not, it will be updated when you reload the page.

Add response and time scales

It is important to add the correct response options and time frames to the item list. It is recommended to use the response options and time frames with which the items were originally validated.

In order to add the response options and time frames you should:

1. Click on Choose a response scale to see the available options

2. Select the appropriate option and click +Add

3. Choose the items to which the chosen option relates

The screenshot shows the 'Questions' interface with the language set to 'English'. A single question is listed: "1. Have you felt nauseated?". To the right, the 'Response scales' section is active, showing a dropdown menu with the selected option "Not at all, A little, Quite a bit, Very much" and an "+ Add" button. Below the dropdown, a text input field contains the text "related questions, e.g. '1-5'", which is highlighted with a red box.

You can type a range:

The screenshot shows the 'Questions' interface with the language set to 'English'. A list of five questions is displayed: "1. Have you felt nauseated?", "2. Have you had pain?", "3. Did you have weakness on one side of your body?", "4. Have you had side-effects from your treatment?", and "5. Have you lost any hair?". To the right, the 'Response scales' section is active, showing a dropdown menu with the selected option "Not at all, A little, Quite a bit, Very much" and an "+ Add" button. Below the dropdown, a text input field contains the text "1-3", which is highlighted with a red box. Below the 'Response scales' section, the 'Time scales' section is visible, showing a dropdown menu with the selected option "Choose a time scale:" and an "+ Add" button. Below the 'Time scales' section, a note reads: "No scale has been defined yet. Don't forget to link scales to your questions, otherwise they won't make sense."

or single numbers separated by commas.

Submit an item list for approval

Once a draft is ready for use, it can be submitted for approval to the IL admin.

The screenshot shows the item list interface. On the left, there is a list of items with a header 'b'. Below the header, there are three columns: 'GENDER' with the value 'Neutral', 'TYPE' with the value 'Module', and 'CREATED' with the value '21 lut 2018'. On the right, there are four buttons: "+ Add item", a button with a document icon, a button with the text "Submit for publishing" (highlighted with a red box), and a button with a trash can icon. Below the buttons, there is a button with a pencil icon.

The IL admin checks to see if the basic information on the item list has been added correctly and if the item list includes all the necessary elements, such as response scale. Once this has been confirmed, the IL admin prepares a user agreement for the use of the item list.

After the user agreement has been fully executed, the IL admin approves the item list for publication in the system. Commercial use of item lists is subject to a license fee.

Modify a submitted item list

An item list that has been submitted for approval cannot be modified. If you would like to modify the submitted draft, you have to first cancel the submission.

Once the submission has been cancelled, the submitted item list reverts to draft status and can be modified by adding, deleting and re-ordering items.

Published item lists

All approved item lists are visible in the Custom questionnaire library. They are accessible to all users of the IL. Only an approved, published item list can be exported.

In order to export an item list, you have to click on the export button.

An exported item list is available as a .csv file that can be opened in, for example, Microsoft Office Excel.

Custom questionnaire translations

It is possible to have the custom item list available in languages other than English. In order to get a translation, you have to follow these steps:

1. Choose the required language. The drop-down list includes all possible languages – which might not be necessarily available for (all) the items. The drop-down list can be refined by typing the name of the language. It also includes different names for the same language (for example, “Korean” and “Korean (South Korea)”), so it is best to check the naming convention used for the EORTC questionnaires in the questionnaire or item view (these lists include only the language in which there are official, available translations).
2. View the translation of the custom item list. Translations are collated automatically from different questionnaires and often from different wordings that are available for one item. The following options are possible:

- If a recommended wording in this language has been set for a particular item, it is chosen for the item.
 - If there is no recommended wording chosen, the most recent translation will be added.
 - If no translation exists, you will see “No translation available” above the English version
3. Review the translation. Because of the fact that translations are pulled from different questionnaires and might be inconsistent, all translations must be reviewed together with the IL admin. Gender-specific items are marked with a gender symbol, because in some languages the translation developed for one gender only will not fit the other gender or a mixed population.
 4. Export the translation. All language versions can be exported into a .csv file.

Use of custom item lists

The use of custom, user-created item lists is subject to the conditions specified in the user agreement and to the user requirements available on the QLG website: <https://qol.eortc.org/>

More specific information can also be obtained by e-mail: itemlibrary@eortc.org

Item classification

The screenshot shows a web application interface with three tabs: "Official questionnaires", "Custom questionnaires", and "Item classification". The "Item classification" tab is selected and active. Below the tabs, there are two sub-sections: "Standard classification" and "CTCAE classification". The "Standard classification" section is expanded, showing a list of categories with their respective item counts:

- + Body Image (31)
- + Bones, Muscles, & Joints (7)
- + Breast (21)
- + Cardiovascular (6)
- + Cognitive Functioning (37)
- + Communication/Speech (9)
- + Dermatological (37)
- + Disease/Treatment Burden (27)
- + Eating/Appetite Loss (42)
- + Edema (14)
- + Emotional Functioning (61)

The Item classification tab contains two item classifications presented in the form of an item tree: the standard classification and the Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE) classification.

The development of the CTCAE classification has been described in a paper by Gilbert, Piccinin et al. entitled “Linking the European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer Item Library to the Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Event” (JCO 40:32, 2022 <https://doi.org/10.1200/jco.21.02017>).

Standard classification

The standard classification is a bottom-up classification based on the content of the items. It includes categories and subcategories that can be displayed by clicking on the plus symbol.

Items belonging to each category are then displayed with their short name and code.

Standard classification | **CTCAE classification**

- + Body Image (31)
- + Bones, Muscles, & Joints (7)
- Breast (21)
 - 🔍 Q134 - pain area affected breast
 - 🔍 Q135 - swollen area affected breast
 - 🔍 Q137 - skin problems area affected breast
 - 🔍 Q258 - problem fullness arm
 - 🔍 Q262 - breast role sexuality
 - 🔍 Q263 - problem loss sensations breast
- + Breast reconstruction (15)

Standard classification | **CTCAE classification**

- + Body Image (31)
- + Bones, Muscles, & Joints (7)
- + Breast (21)
- + Cardiovascular (6)
- + Cognitive Functioning (37)
- + Communication/Speech (9)
- + Dermatological (37)
- + Disease/Treatment Burden (27)
- + Eating/Appetite Loss (42)
- + Edema (14)
- + Emotional Functioning (61)
- + Emotional Impact of Symptom, Diagnosis, or Treatment (122)
- + Family Life (16)
- + Fatigue (38)
- + Financial Impact (1)
- + Fine Motor Skills (4)
- + Future Outlook (30)
- + Gastrointestinal (56)
- + General Physical Health (79)
- + Global Health & QOL (2)
- + Impact on Life & Daily Activities (85)
- + Information/Satisfaction with Care (228)
- + Medication/Medical Device Use (32)
- + Not Classified (168)
- + Oral (36)
- + Pain (79)
- + Physical Functioning (66)
- + Recreation/Leisure (3)
- + Reproductive/Sexual (21)
- + Respiratory (6)
- + Role Functioning (11)
- + Screening Items (0)
- + Sensory/Neurological (21)
- + Sleep (10)
- + Social Functioning (0)
- + Spirituality (21)
- + Surgery (5)
- + Urinary (14)

CTCAE classification

The CTCAE classification is based on the standardised categories (from the CTCAE v5.0) used by clinicians to describe adverse events. Items that do not relate to CTCAE cancer issues and those that have not yet been classified are listed as Not classified.

Standard classification | CTCAE classification

- + Cardiac disorders (6)
- + Ear and labyrinth disorders (5)
- + Endocrine disorders (3)
- + Eye disorders (85)
- + Gastrointestinal disorders (304)
- + General disorders and administration site conditions (320)
- + Immune system disorders (2)
- + Infections and infestations (13)
- + Injury, poisoning and procedural complications (24)
- + Investigations (33)
- + Metabolism and nutrition disorders (18)
- + Musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders (101)
- + Nervous system disorders (286)
- + Not classified (405)
- + Psychiatric disorders (107)
- + Renal and urinary disorders (30)
- + Reproductive system and breast disorders (93)
- + Respiratory, thoracic and mediastinal disorders (118)
- + Skin and subcutaneous tissue disorders (75)
- + Surgical and medical procedures (8)
- + Vascular disorders (11)